

dmTP: A Deep Meta-learning based Framework for Mobile Traffic Prediction

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Abstract—Deep learning technologies have been widely exploited to predict mobile traffic. However, individually training deep learning models for various traffic prediction tasks is not only time consuming but also unrealistic sometimes due to limited traffic records. In this article, we propose a novel deep meta-learning based mobile traffic prediction framework, namely, dmTP, which can adaptively learn to learn the proper prediction model for each distinct prediction task from accumulated meta-knowledge of previously learned prediction tasks. In dmTP, we regard each mobile traffic prediction task as a base-task and adopt a long short-term memory (LSTM) network with a fixed structure as the base-learner for each base-task. In order to improve the base-learner’s prediction accuracy and learning efficiency, we further employ a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) as the meta-learner to find the optimal hyper-parameter value and initial training status for the base-learner of a new base-task according to its meta-features. Extensive experiments with real-world datasets demonstrate that while guaranteeing a similar or even better prediction accuracy, meta-learning in the proposed dmTP reduces the numbers of epochs and base-samples needed to train the base-learners by around 75% and 81%, respectively, as compared with the existing prediction models.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the popularity of mobile devices and applications such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and virtual reality (VR)/augmented reality (AR), mobile communication networks have become an indispensable part of people’s lives [1]. According to Cisco’s latest statistical report [2], the global mobile service demands was predicted to increase seven-fold from 2016 to 2021 and account for 20 percent of the total Internet traffic by 2021. In order to support such rapidly growing mobile services [1-2], key technical challenges in mobile traffic analysis, including mobile traffic prediction, anomaly detection, attack classification, website fingerprinting, and mobile traffic identification, have been widely studied in recent years [3]. Among these challenges, the accurate prediction of mobile traffic is a critical enabler of advanced management and optimization of network resources.

Mobile traffic prediction has attracted continued research interest from both academia and industry [4-11]. Estimating the future traffic loads based on historical traffic records, mobile traffic prediction has been widely considered as a time series forecasting problem. The existing mobile traffic prediction models or algorithms can be generally classified

into two categories: statistical methods and machine learning based methods [4].

In statistical methods, researchers tried to use explicit statistical models with certain parameters to fit the mobile traffic patterns for future traffic forecasting. In [5], Zhou et al. used the linear autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model to capture the short-term correlation in network traffic. The seasonal ARIMA model was adopted in [6] to capture the long-term traffic correlation. Li et al. [7] demonstrated that the cellular traffic loads generated by three typical mobile services follow heavy-tailed distributions and then proposed to utilize the α -stable model to predict their load fluctuations. However, since realistic mobile traffic tends to show complex irregular patterns, it is difficult for statistical models to accurately predict realistic mobile traffic.

Machine learning technologies are gaining increasing popularity in mobile traffic prediction recently. Unlike the statistical methods, machine learning based methods package the statistical models used for prediction into opaque or semi-opaque black-boxes, which need to be trained using historical traffic records. In [8] and [9], linear regression (LR) and support vector regression (SVR) were used to predict the network-level mobile traffic, respectively. Nevertheless, these shallow learning methods cannot cope with many practical prediction scenarios due to the fact that they cannot perform feature extraction on their own, but also rely on some prior knowledge of the input features. Recently, powerful deep learning tools have been leveraged for mobile traffic prediction. Nie et al. [10] employed a deep belief network based model to predict the mobile traffic loads aggregated over a city. Based on traffic information for neighboring cells, Feng et al. [11] proposed a long short-term memory (LSTM) network based prediction model to forecast the traffic loads in the target cell. With a reduced connection complexity, a model based on a random connectivity LSTM network was proposed in [12] to predict traffic in a single cell. Furthermore, based on historical traffic loads generated in all the cells, a convolutional neural network (CNN) based prediction model [13] and a convolutional LSTM network based prediction model [4] were proposed to forecast the spatial mobile traffic in a city. However, in the existing works, a specific prediction model must be constructed and trained for each individual mobile traffic prediction task as the time series of mobile traffic handled by various prediction tasks are quite different. Separately training the prediction models for multiple tasks is not only time consuming but also unrealistic since there are not always sufficient historical traffic records available, e.g., for newly built areas.

To fill in the above gaps, this article presents an early

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Dataset 1	Location	Duration	Items
Mobile network traffic	Milan, Italy	11/01/2013-01/01/2014	319,896,289 records
Description: Records provided by <i>Telecom Italy</i> with a temporal interval of 10 minutes. Milan city area is divided into 9,999 grids and the size of a grid is about $235 \times 235 m^2$. Each traffic record has the information about its time interval, geographical grid, and data volume in bits.			
Dataset 2	Location	Duration	Items
Short message service traffic	Guangzhou, China	03/01/2019-03/31/2019	1,521,005 records
Description: Records provided by <i>Unicom China</i> . Each short message service record has the information about its time-stamp and data volume.			
Dataset 3	Location	Duration	Items
Twitter	London, U.K.	02/15/2016-02/28/2016	136,710 records
Description: Twitter records purchased from the <i>Twitter Company</i> . Each record has the information about its time-stamp and city target.			

Fig. 1. Description of the three adopted Datasets.

attempt to introduce deep meta-learning into mobile traffic prediction and investigate how to make the prediction model learn to learn for a specific mobile traffic prediction task according to its characteristics (meta-features). The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- Through fast Fourier transform (FFT), we demonstrate that the temporal variations of mobile traffic over hours, days, and weeks can be characterized by five main frequency components of the frequency spectrum. More specifically, our analysis shows that the Pearson correlation coefficient of the normalized traffic load series for two base-tasks is negatively correlated with the Euclidean distance between their frequency component vectors. In other words, the normalized traffic load series for two base-tasks tend to have similar time domain variations if their frequency component vectors are close to each other, and vice versa.
- We introduce deep meta-learning into mobile traffic prediction, where each prediction task is regarded as a base-task and is represented as a time series forecasting problem. By defining the meta-task as learning to learn the proper prediction models for different base-tasks, we propose a novel deep meta-learning based mobile traffic prediction framework (dmTP). In dmTP, we adopt an L-STM network with a fixed structure as the base-learner to forecast the traffic load for a base-task based on previous values. Using the five main frequency components as the meta-features, we employ a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) as the meta-learner to output the optimal hyper-parameter value and initial status for the base-learner of a new base-task according to the accumulated meta-knowledge and meta-features of the base-task.
- The performance of dmTP is evaluated by extensive tests using real-world mobile traffic data for heterogeneous prediction tasks. Numerical results show that the meta-learning technology not only improves the prediction accuracy and learning efficiency but also makes the base-learners more adaptable to abnormal traffic patterns.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section II presents the statistical characteristics of mobile traffic and briefly introduces the meta-learning technology. Section III

elaborates the proposed dmTP. In Section IV, we evaluate the performance of dmTP in comparison with some existing prediction models. In Section V, we summarize our study.

II. DATASET DESCRIPTION AND BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE OF META-LEARNING

A. Mobile Traffic Traces

In this article, we adopt three real-world mobile traffic datasets generated in Milan (Dataset 1), Guangzhou (Dataset 2), and London (Dataset 3), respectively. Fig. 1 provides the details about those datasets. Dataset 1 is publicly available [4], while Datasets 2 and 3 were purchased and are not publicly accessible.

We refer to each grid in Dataset 1 as a cell and regard the forecasting problem for each cell's mobile traffic load as an individual prediction task. As the city area of Milan is divided into 9,999 grids, there are 9,999 prediction tasks for Dataset 1. For Datasets 2 and 3, we choose the forecasting problem for short message service (SMS) traffic load generated in the whole Guangzhou city and that for Twitter traffic load generated in the whole London city as two prediction tasks, respectively. These prediction tasks from Datasets 1, 2, and 3 focus on different spatial scales and involve different kinds of mobile traffic. Our study does not breach user privacy, or raises ethical or legal issues. Indeed, we do not process individual or personal data. Also, the datasets are strongly anonymized by the geographical aggregation at the cellular or city level, which ensures that the mobile demands are merged over numerous subscribers.

B. Characteristics of Mobile Traffic

We set the time interval resolution at one hour following the settings in [4] mainly because time interval resolutions smaller than one hour will result in the situation that many cells from Dataset 1 have lots of zero values in their traffic load series, which will be too sparse for traffic prediction. The peak traffic loads among various prediction tasks from the three datasets differ by up to 5 orders of magnitude and we normalize the traffic load series of each prediction task into the range of [0,1] using the max-min scaling method.

Fig. 2. Characteristics of mobile traffic in time domain and frequency domain: a) temporal patterns of three mobile traffic time series (network traffic generated in cell 1684 in Milan, SMS traffic generated in Guangzhou, and Twitter traffic generated in London); b) FFT results of those time series in a); c) CDF of base-tasks whose sum energy of the five main frequency components accounts a certain percentage of the related periodic signal's energy; d) dependencies of time series pairs in both time domain and frequency domain.

Fig. 2(a) illustrates the normalized mobile traffic loads in three prediction tasks during two weeks. We observe that though the three mobile traffic streams exhibit different temporal patterns, they all exhibit a weekly cyclic pattern, which is also observed in time series of other cells from Dataset 1.

We generate a discrete periodic signal for each mobile traffic prediction task by periodically repeating its normalized real traffic loads in the first secular week (from Monday to Sunday) and then perform fast Fourier transform (FFT) of it. Please note that although the constructed periodic signal only approximates the actual mobile traffic load series, it allows us to capture the main features of a prediction task with much fewer records of historical traffic loads. Fig. 2(b) shows the amplitudes of the frequency components in the FFT results related to the three time series in Fig. 2(a). From Fig. 2(b), we find that in the frequency domain, $\omega = \pi/84, \pi/12, \pi/6, \pi/4, \pi/3$ (corresponding to the periods of one week, one day, 12 hours, 8 hours, and 6 hours, respectively) are the five main frequency components for a mobile traffic prediction task. However, the amplitudes of the main frequency components vary evidently across different prediction tasks. Fig. 2(c) shows the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the signal energy carried by the five main frequency components. We observe that the sum energy of the five main frequency components in more than 60 percent of the considered prediction tasks exceeds 60 percent of the signal energy.

We use a frequency component vector of size 10 to record the real parts and imaginary parts of a prediction task's main frequency components. Obviously, this vector can reflect both the amplitude and the phase of each main frequency component. Fig. 2(d) illustrates inter-dependencies of 5,000 randomly selected pairs of time series (i.e., prediction tasks) from Dataset 1 in both time domain and the corresponding frequency domain. Specifically, Fig. 2(d) plots the Euclidean distance between the two frequency component vectors of a pair of prediction tasks versus the Pearson correlation coefficient between the two corresponding time series. It can be observed that the Pearson correlation coefficient of two prediction tasks' time series is negatively correlated with the Euclidean distance between their frequency component vectors. In other words, two prediction tasks' time series tend to have similar time domain variations if their frequency component vectors are close to each other, and vice versa. This

implies that the frequency component vector can be used to characterize the features of a prediction task's traffic pattern.

C. Meta-Learning

Meta-learning studies how learning systems can increase learning efficiency through experience. The goal of meta-learning is to understand how learning itself can become flexible according to the domains or tasks under study [14].

For a typical supervised learning task ξ and a learner ς , each sample is denoted by labeling a number of features with an unknown target function F_ξ and the hypothesis space of learner ς , \mathcal{H}_ς , is defined as the set of all the possible hypothesis functions generated by ς . The training progress of ς can thus be seen as searching the hypothesis function $h_\varsigma(\xi)$ that approximates F_ξ over ς 's hypothesis space. ς usually embeds a set of **biases**, which may be caused by the adopted learning algorithm, hyper-parameters, or the initial status. These biases may restrict the size of a base-learner's hypothesis space, and will affect how the base-learner searches the hypothesis space. Meta-learning matches the biases of a base-learner to an individual task, which is achieved by a meta-task that adaptively generates a proper set of biases for each learning task according to the learning task's meta-features. The meta-task itself can be seen as a learning task and handled by a meta-learner. Accordingly, those original individual learning tasks are referred to as base-tasks.

III. THE PROPOSED DMTP

Fig. 3 shows the diagram of our proposed deep meta-learning based mobile traffic prediction framework, dmTP. In dmTP, we regard each individual mobile traffic prediction task as a base-task and present an LSTM network based prediction model with a fixed structure as the base-learner for it. We define a base-task's frequency component vector as its meta-features. We regard the number of steps, which is a hyper-parameter defining the length of the input sequence and is denoted by SN , and the initial values of neural connection weights and neural thresholds as a base-learner's set of biases. For each considered value of SN , the hypothesis space of a base-learner is composed of the mappings each of which transforms the $3 \times SN$ -dimensional input sequence into an $1 \times SN$ -dimensional output sequence. Thus, the value of SN determines a base-learner's hypothesis space and the initial

Fig. 3. Architecture of the proposed dmTP framework.

parameter values determine the base-learner's initial searching point in its hypothesis space.

Intuitively, since the meta-features of a base-task reflect the characteristics of its traffic pattern, the best set of biases of the base-learner will be influenced by this task's meta-features¹. We use an MLP as the meta-learner to implicitly extract the correlation between the base-tasks' meta-features and their best sets of biases, and output the best set of biases for a new base-task's base-learner according to the meta-features.

Notations in dmTP: S_{train}^{meta} denotes the meta-task training set, which is equivalent to the set of base-tasks generating meta-samples for meta-task training. For base-task m in S_{train}^{meta} , we use $S_{train_large}^{base_m(SN)}$ to denote the large base-task training set of base-samples for training m 's base-learner when the number of steps equals SN , while use $S_{verify}^{base_m(SN)}$ to denote the set of base-samples for verifying the base-learner's performance. For base-task n not in S_{train}^{meta} , we use $S_{train_small}^{base_n(SN_n^*)}$ to denote the small base-task training set with few base-samples for fine-tuning the base-learner and use $S_{test}^{base_n(SN_n^*)}$ to denote the set of base-samples for testing the base-learner's performance.

¹For a base-learner with a fixed structure and a set of base-samples obtained from the traffic load series of a base-task, the optimal number of steps and parameter values making the base-learner optimally fit those base-samples are determined by the frequency characteristics of the base-task's traffic load series since these frequency characteristics can completely reflect the temporal pattern of the traffic load series. As shown in Fig. 2, the frequency characteristics of a base-task's traffic load series are generally dominated by the five main frequency components and the frequency component vector composed of them can characterize the features of a base-task's traffic pattern. Hence, we select the frequency component vector as the meta-features of each base-task. Our additional experiment results (not presented in this article) show that enriching the meta-features with more than five frequency components will not significantly further improve the meta-learner's performance.

 Fig. 4. Detailed structure of an LSTM memory block. \oplus and \otimes denote summation and dot product of two vectors, respectively. $\sigma(x)$ takes the sigmoid function, and $\varphi(x)$ takes the hyperbolic tangent function.

A. LSTM Network as the Base-learner

In dmTP, we construct a multi-layer LSTM network with Q layers to act as the base-learner. For a specific prediction task, this LSTM network will be continuously fed with a sequence of input vectors related to previous SN time intervals and predict (as the output) normalized mobile traffic load in the next time interval. Each input vector consists of three attributes: the normalized mobile traffic load, the day of the week, and the hour of the day.

Fig. 4 gives the structure of an LSTM memory block in the q th layer of the base-learner. An LSTM memory block is logically a recurrently connected subnet containing some functional modules called gates. As shown in Fig. 4, if the LSTM memory block's input vector and output vector are of size U_q and V_q , respectively, there will be $p_q = 4 \cdot (U_q + V_q) \cdot V_q + 4 \cdot V_q$ parameters to be trained in the q th layer. Thus, the total number of parameters to be trained in a base-learner is

given by $P = p_1 + \dots + p_Q$.

B. Train the Meta-learner with Meta-samples

We assume that a base-learner will obtain high prediction accuracy and training efficiency when its SN value determines the proper hypothesis space and its initial parameters approach the target ones (the initial searching point in the hypothesis space approaches the target function) [14].

The dmTP utilizes a set of base-tasks to construct S_{train}^{meta} . For each base-task m in S_{train}^{meta} , the best value of SN for its base-learner is selected from multiple candidates through exhaustive trials. Specifically, for every candidate value, SN^c , the base-learner is trained using $S_{train_large}^{base_m(SN^c)}$ with randomly selected initial values of the P parameters and its performance is verified via $S_{verify}^{base_m(SN^c)}$. All the base-samples in $S_{train_large}^{base_m(SN^c)}$ and $S_{verify}^{base_m(SN^c)}$ have the same length of input sequence, SN^c . The best SN value that leads to the base-learner's highest prediction accuracy is then selected and denoted by SN_m^* . By labeling base-task m 's frequency component vector with SN_m^* and P parameters of the base-learner trained by $S_{train_large}^{base_m(SN_m^*)}$, one meta-sample is obtained.

We propose to construct the meta-learner with MLP, which consists of at least three layers of operations [15]. We train the MLP based meta-learner using S_{train}^{meta} . With the MLP's ability of feature extraction and correlation characterization [15], the meta-learner will be able to generate the best step number, SN_n^* , and initial parameter values approaching the target ones for the base-learner of a new base-task n .

C. Fine-tune the Base-learner for a New Base-task

As shown in Fig. 3, for a new mobile traffic prediction task (i.e., a new base-task) n , the frequency component vector is first extracted as its meta-features. The well-trained meta-learner is fed with the meta-features and outputs a set of biases for the base-learner of base-task n .

The base-learner will take the given SN_n^* as its number of steps and set its initial values of neural connection weights and neural thresholds according to the output of the meta-learner. Then, the base-learner is fine-tuned using the small base-task training set, $S_{train_small}^{base_n(SN_n^*)}$. With meta-knowledge, the base-learner of base-task n is expected to obtain a good prediction accuracy and training efficiency in terms of a fast convergence speed and a small number of base-samples needed. $S_{train_small}^{base_n(SN_n^*)}$ can only contain a few base-samples to guarantee the base-learner's prediction accuracy.

IV. EVALUATION ON REAL-WORLD MOBILE TRAFFIC DATA

A. Experimental Settings

In our experiments, the base-learner is constructed as a three-layer LSTM network, where the output vectors of the first and the second LSTM memory blocks are both of size 5. According to the LSTM memory block structure, the total number of parameters to be trained for each base-learner is 428. The meta-learner has 3 hidden layers of size 300, 300, and 400, respectively, while its input and output layers have

10 neurons and 429 neurons (one for SN and the rest for the 428 parameters in a base-learner to be trained), respectively².

We randomly select 8,000 out of 9,999 base-tasks from Dataset 1 to construct the meta-training set, S_{train}^{meta} . For each base-task m in S_{train}^{meta} , we test SN from 3 to 24. For a candidate SN value, SN^c , we apply a sliding window with size SN^c to split m 's normalized traffic load series and generate the base-samples by labeling each sequence of input vectors with the normalized traffic load in next time interval. We randomly select 90 percent of these base-samples to construct $S_{train_large}^{base_m(SN^c)}$ while use the remaining ones to construct $S_{verify}^{base_m(SN^c)}$. We examine the performance of dmTP on the remaining 1,999 base-tasks of Dataset 1 that have not been selected for meta-training and the two testing base-tasks from Datasets 2 and 3. Similarly, for each testing base-task n , we apply a sliding window with size SN_n^* , which is output by the meta-learner, to generate the base-samples.

The performance of dmTP is compared with the existing time series forecasting methods including ARIMA [5], LR [8], SVR [9], and basic LSTM networks [12] for $SN = 12, 24$. For a fair comparison, we construct the basic LSTM network with the same structure of a base-learner in dmTP. We choose the mean square error (MSE) as the loss function, while the adaptive moment estimation algorithm [15] with the default learning rate is utilized to optimize the baseline LSTM networks as well as the meta-learner and base-learners in dmTP. We note that for around 20 percent of the base-tasks in Dataset 1, the traffic loads in more than 50 percent of time intervals are lower than 20 percent of the peak traffic load, while for around 84 percent of the base-tasks in Dataset 1 and the two base-tasks from Datasets 2 and 3, the traffic loads in more than 50 percent of time intervals are lower than 40 percent of the peak traffic load. Considering that the mean values of the traffic load series related to a significant portion of base-tasks are relatively low, we use the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) to evaluate the accuracy of the considered prediction methods.

B. Prediction Performance

Fig. 5(a)-(d) compare the prediction accuracy achieved by dmTP and the baseline methods. In order to test the applicability of meta-learning technology to other prediction methods, we evaluate the performance of ARIMA, LR, and SVR when their hyper-parameters (i.e., the number of steps for ARIMA and LR, and the kernel function for SVR) for a certain base-task are either fixed or selected by MLP based meta-learners from multiple candidate values (where candidate SN value ranges from 1 to 5 for ARIMA, candidate SN value ranges from 1 to 10 for LR, and candidate kernel functions for SVR are linear, poly, and exponential functions). Except for the output layer, the meta-learners for the above three baseline methods have the same structure as the meta-learner in dmTP. For each testing base-task from Dataset 1, the testing base-samples are generated during the two weeks of 12/16/2013-

²In practice, other structures of the meta-learner as well as the base-learners can be adopted in the proposed framework. However, finding the optimal structures for the learning models is outside the scope of this work.

Fig. 5. Performance of dmTP and the baseline methods: a) average NRMSE achieved over testing base-tasks from Dataset 1 (normal traffic); b) NRMSE for base-task related to Dataset 2; c) NRMSE for base-task related to Dataset 3; d) average NRMSE achieved over testing base-tasks from Dataset 1 (abnormal traffic); e) Prediction results of the dmTP and the basic LSTM networks for a testing base-task in Dataset 1 (cell 1684); f) ATT and TCMTM needed by dmTP and the baseline methods.

12/22/2013 and 12/23/2013-12/29/2013, where the traffic pattern during the second week has obvious abnormalities due to the Christmas holidays. For the two testing base-tasks from Datasets 2 and 3, the testing base-samples are generated in the last week, i.e., 03/25/2019-03/31/2019 and 02/22/2016-02/28/2016, respectively. Note that for each testing base-task in Fig. 5, all the base-samples that have not been used for testing are used to fine-tune/train the base-learner in dmTP and the baseline models.

As can be seen from Fig. 5(a)-(d), ARIMA and LR perform poorly among all the considered methods. This is because these simple models are not able to capture the highly non-linear temporal patterns of mobile traffic loads. The SVR, which is a nonlinear prediction method, can deal with the nonlinearities in load variation, and thus achieves better performance than that of ARIMA and LR. Due to the deep learning capability, the basic LSTM networks with adequate training data are able to learn the deep dependency between traffic loads generated in various time intervals, and thus perform better than ARIMA, LR, and SVR, as shown in Fig. 5(a). However, Fig. 5(b) and (c) show that the prediction accuracy of the basic LSTM networks degrades for prediction tasks related to Datasets 2 and 3. This is because the basic LSTM networks require a large number of samples to train their models. The small training sets with base-samples generated in a three-week or one-week period will result in overfitting and thus poor performance. Fig. 5(d) shows that when there are abnormalities in the testing traffic patterns, the basic LSTM networks have unsatisfactory performance as well. This is because these basic LSTM networks have high dependency on the training data and will fail to predict the abnormal traffic loads if there are no similar samples in their training sets.

The proposed dmTP always obtains the best prediction accuracy, attributing to two aspects. First, the base-learner for each base-task in dmTP has the ability of learning and representing the complex nonlinearities in mobile traffic load

variations. Second, unlike the basic LSTM networks embedded with fixed hyper-parameters and randomly selected initial parameter values, the meta-learner in dmTP will find the best SN and proper initial values of parameters for a base-learner, which leads to a higher prediction accuracy and a stronger adaptability to the abnormal traffic pattern. Compared with ARIMA, LR, and SVR, dmTP reduces the NRMSE by about 25-43 percent, 73-85 percent, and 20-39 percent, respectively, for the testing base-tasks from Datasets 1, 2, and 3. As shown in Fig. 5(a), when there is adequate training data and the traffic pattern is normal, dmTP can further reduce the NRMSE by 12 percent compared with the basic LSTM networks mainly because of the selection of the optimal SN value. As shown in Fig. 5(b)-(d), when the training sets are small or the traffic pattern is abnormal, dmTP outperforms the basic LSTM networks with a 28-60 percent reduction in NRMSE owing to the proper selection of initial parameter values in each base-learner. Fig. 5(e) shows the prediction results of dmTP and the basic LSTM networks for a testing base-task in Dataset 1 (cell 1684). We can clearly see that dmTP achieves more accurate prediction values than the basic LSTM networks when the traffic pattern has abnormalities or sudden changes. From Fig. 5, we also find that the three baseline methods in conjunction with meta-learning technology perform better than their counterparts without meta-learning technology, and the meta-learners can improve the prediction accuracy by about 9 percent, 17 percent, and 8 percent, for ARIMA, LR, and SVR, respectively. These results confirm the applicability of the meta-learning technology to ARIMA, LR, and SVR.

Fig 5(f) shows the average training time (ATT) needed by the base-learners in dmTP and the baseline methods for the testing base-tasks as well as the time needed to construct the meta-task training set and train the meta-learner (TCMTM). Compared with the baseline methods, although dmTP consumes much more TCMTM, after the initial parameter values have been properly set, the base-learner of a new base-task will

converge faster and need shorter ATT than the basic LSTM networks. Note that since the meta-samples can be obtained off-line and the meta-learner only needs to be trained once, the extra off-line complexity caused by meta-learning in dmTP can be justified by the improved on-line convergence speed and reduced training time of base-learners.

C. Learning Efficiency Improvement for Base-learner

In Fig. 6, we use the testing base-tasks from Dataset 1 to further examine how the meta-learner can help the base-learners improve their learning efficiency in terms of convergence speed and the number of base-samples needed. For each testing base-task, the testing base-samples are generated during the two weeks of 12/16/2013-12/22/2013 and 12/23/2013-12/29/2013, while different from Fig. 5, only a portion of the remaining base-samples are randomly selected to fine-tune/train the base-learner in dmTP and the baseline models.

Fig 6(a) shows the average NRMSE achieved by the proposed dmTP, basic LSTM networks with random initial parameters, and the LSTM network with biases transferred from a certain base-task in S_{train}^{meta} (cell 6395 with the best SN of 6) versus the number of epochs in training, where 840 base-samples are used to fine-tune/train the base-learner in dmTP and the baseline models for each testing base-task. We can see that for predicting normal mobile traffic, the NRMSE for basic LSTM networks decreases as the number of epochs increases and remains at a good accuracy level after 40 epochs. Due to the diversity of mobile traffic patterns among various base-tasks, the LSTM network with transferred biases has slower convergence speed and higher NRMSE than dmTP, but the transferred initial parameters result in lower initial NRMSE value and higher convergence speed than the basic LSTM networks. The dmTP's performance becomes stable after 10 epochs, leading to a 75 percent reduction in the number of epochs needed than the basic LSTM networks. Thanks to the chosen optimal SN value, dmTP reduces the NRMSE by about 12 percent as compared with the basic LSTM networks. We can also see that for predicting abnormal mobile traffic, dmTP has much faster convergence speed than both the basic LSTM networks and the LSTM network with transferred biases. Moreover, the accuracy improvement for dmTP over the baselines after they all become stable is much larger than that for predicting normal mobile traffic. This demonstrates that the meta-learner can not only elevate the base-learners' learning efficiency but also make them more adaptable to abnormal mobile traffic because the accumulated meta-knowledge will help each base-learner in dmTP handle unknown traffic patterns.

Fig. 6(b) displays the average NRMSE achieved by dmTP and the baselines versus the number of training base-samples selected to fine-tune/train the predicting models for each testing base-task with 100 training epochs. We can see that for predicting normal mobile traffic, the basic LSTM networks and the LSTM network with transferred biases obtain a high prediction accuracy if the base-task training sets are large enough (e.g., more than 500 training base-samples). The prediction accuracy of dmTP with 150 training base-samples exceeds

that of the basic LSTM networks with 800 training base-samples. Compared with the basic LSTM networks, the meta-learner in dmTP helps the base-learners reduce the training base-samples needed by about 81 percent. Since each base-learner for a testing base-task in dmTP is given a proper set of biases by the meta-learner, only a limited number of base-samples are required to fine-tune a base-learner to achieve high accuracy. For predicting abnormal traffic, the NRMSE for dmTP is significantly lower than those for the basic LSTM networks and the LSTM network with transferred biases. This is because without meta-knowledge, the LSTM networks will fail to accurately predict unknown traffic patterns if there are no similar base-samples in their training sets.

V. CONCLUSION

By taking each individual mobile traffic prediction task as a base-task and the main frequency components of traffic time series as a base-task's meta-features, we have constructed a meta-task that can adaptively learn to learn the proper hyper-parameter and initial parameter values based on accumulated meta-knowledge for the prediction model of a new base-task. Specifically, we adopt an LSTM network with a fixed structure as the base-learner for each base-task while proposing an MLP based meta-learner for the meta-task.

The prediction accuracy of the proposed dmTP framework has been tested on multiple real-world mobile traffic datasets. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed framework is able to forecast the mobile traffic loads for prediction tasks with quite different spacial scales or application types. With meta-learning, the proposed framework can achieve a much higher prediction accuracy than the existing prediction methods. Moreover, the meta-learner will lead to about 75 percent and 81 percent reduction in epochs and base-samples needed to fine-tune the base-learners compared with traditional LSTM network based prediction models.

Building on this work, it will be interesting to mathematically model and analyze the correlation between a base-task's frequency component vector and the best set of biases for the task's base-learner, as well as investigate whether the meta-learning technology can be used to optimize the structure of the base-learner for a prediction task. Additionally, it is worth studying if some other characteristics of mobile traffic patterns can be used as a base-task's meta-features.

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Fig. 6. Performance of dmTP and basic LSTM networks under different numbers of training epochs and different numbers of base-samples: a) NRMSE versus the number of training epochs; b) NRMSE versus the number of training base-samples.

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